

Impact of Adverse Childhood Experiences on Achievement Orientation among School Children in Enugu State

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Abstract : This study investigated the impact of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) on achievement orientation among school children in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted an ex-post-facto research design. A sample of 471 school children who met the inclusion criteria drawn through purposive sampling techniques was used. The Adverse Childhood Experience Questionnaire (ACEQ) and Students' Achievement Orientation Questionnaire (SAOQ) were the instruments used for data collection. Means, standard deviation and ANOVA were used for data analysis. Major findings revealed that school children who are vulnerable to ACEs manifest a lower achievement orientation than those who are not/less vulnerable, irrespective of gender. The results suggested, among other things, that educators, parents, and caregivers be made aware of the negative impact of ACEs on children and adults, as well as preventative strategies that can be implemented at the home, school, and community levels. This action could improve the prevention and lessen the effects of childhood adversities among school children in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Achievement orientation, Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs), Enugu State, gender, school children

1. Introduction

Early childhood experiences play a foundational role in shaping a child's growth and well-being. According to Music (2016), children encounter a variety of experiences that contribute to their overall development. The experiences an individual encounter before the age of eighteen whether positive or negative can have lasting effects on cognitive, emotional, and academic functioning, depending on their nature and intensity (Connolly, 2020). Positive childhood experiences tend to support healthy development while negative childhood experiences also referred to as adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) include various forms of abuse, neglect, and household dysfunction (Center for Disease Control & Prevention, 2016).

ACEs can impair children's growth and academic success. According to Barboza (2018), ACEs often occur as cumulative traumatic exposures than isolated and can cause physical, emotional, and structural harm that can severely impede a child's overall development. Research has consistently linked ACEs to poor emotional regulation, reduced cognitive functioning, and negative educational outcomes among children (Soleimanpour, Geierstanger, & Brindis, 2017; Ding & He, 2021).

A recent study indicated that more than half (54%) of adolescents aged 12 to 17 have experienced at least one or more ACEs (Soleimanpour, Geierstanger, & Brindis, 2017). In Nigeria, many children face adverse childhood experiences daily, including children in Enugu State. A study by Agbaje et al. (2021) reported that many students in Enugu state have been exposed to difficulties and traumatic experiences such as abuse, neglect, and violence. Research has consistently linked ACEs to poor emotional regulation, reduced cognitive functioning, and poor educational outcomes among children (Ding & He, 2021).

Achievement orientation is one educational outcome that may be particularly affected by ACEs. Achievement orientation refers to how individuals interpret and respond to challenges, shaping their

thoughts, emotions, and behaviours (Alhadabi & Karpinski, 2020). It encompasses motivation, determination, goal-setting, persistence, and drive, all of which are critical for personal and societal development (Nuamah, 2018). This implies that achievement orientation shapes how children approach learning tasks and cope with success or failure in school. A study conducted by Niemivirta, Pulkka, Tapola, and Tuominen (2019) reported that achievement-oriented individuals tend to have greater confidence, while those who lack confidence may struggle to reach their goals. Highly achievement-oriented individuals often develop a strong sense of identity and successfully pursue career objectives. Conversely, those with low achievement orientation may experience poor self-awareness and fail to realise their potential. Schoolchildren with high achievement orientation tend to show higher engagement and persistence, while those with weak orientation may avoid challenging tasks and struggle academically. Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) describe school children as learners in post-primary education who are undergoing structured instruction aimed at developing academic, social, and vocational competencies. School children in this study are learners enrolled in the junior secondary school, typically between the ages of late childhood.

In this study, we investigate how different achievement orientation affect students' learning with respect to their exposure to ACEs. Each of these orientations explains various task performances that the children might value. Based on that, children's achievement orientation is commonly described in three forms including mastery orientation, performance orientation, and avoidance orientation (Chukwuma, 2016). Mastery-oriented children focus on learning and self-improvement, performance-oriented children emphasise grades and competition, while avoidance-oriented children are motivated by fear of failure. Studies suggest that exposure to ACEs can hinder the development of high achievement orientation, leading to reduced motivation, poor goal-setting, and disengagement from

learning (Brumley et al., 2017; Nieuwenhuis & Chiang, 2021). Similarly, Adverse childhood experiences can hamper the formation of achievement orientation (O'Donnell & Oyserman, 2022). McGaha-Garneth (2013) and Lloyd (2018) in their studies found that children exposed to violence have a 13% higher likelihood of quitting school, jeopardising their future prospects. Page | 28

Given that ACEs impair emotional regulation and cognitive functioning (Soleimanpour et al., 2017), it is reasonable to hypothesise that students with higher ACE exposure may exhibit lower achievement orientation. Children who experience high levels of adversity may struggle to focus, set functional life goals, and maintain engagement in tasks. In contrast, those with fewer or no adverse experiences are more likely to be organised and motivated to succeed. McClellan (2019) established a relationship between economic growth and achievement orientation. It has been discovered that countries with a large number of people with high achievement orientation tend to have high rates of academic achievement and economic development when compared to those with lower achievement orientation.

Several studies have documented the intellectual difficulties, developmental setbacks, and academic struggles among children with adverse childhood experience (Bick & Nelson, 2016; Altamini, Almuneef, Abuhairan, & Saleheen, 2017). Neglected children are more likely to become truant, perform poorly in school, struggle with concentration, associate with delinquent peers, and drop out before completing secondary education (Bick & Nelson, 2016; Child Welfare Information Gateway, 2018). McGaha-Garneth (2013) and Lloyd (2018) found that children exposed to violence have a 13% higher likelihood of quitting school, jeopardising their future prospects. Despite these findings, limited research has specifically examined how ACEs influence achievement orientation among school children, particularly in Enugu State Nigeria.

Achievement orientation can also vary by gender. The term gender is utilized to make distinctions between male and female based on characteristics which are attributed to them as either masculine or feminine. Gender is defined as socio-cultural attributes and responsibilities that define one as male or female student. Research supports the assumption that gender differences influence achievement orientation (Eze & Ngwoke, 2018). Musa, Dauda, and Umar (2016) observed a significant gender influence on mastery goal orientation, favouring males. Additionally, males with a history of ACE exposure often require significant psychological support, suggesting that gender may influence the impact of adversity on achievement orientation (Lukaszewski, 2020). However, it remains unclear whether males exhibit higher achievement orientation or experience more ACEs than females. Due to this uncertainty, the study incorporates gender as a comparison variable in examining the impact of ACEs on achievement orientation.

Therefore, this study examined the impact of adverse childhood experiences on achievement orientation among school children. By understanding this relationship, the study sought to highlight the need to address adverse childhood experiences to improve motivation and engagement in learning and life outcomes among school children.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Every child in an educational setting should have opportunities to learn, develop positive achievement goals and aspire toward personal and academic success. Achievement orientation plays a crucial role in students' academic success and future life outcomes. Children should grow in safe and stable environment where their physical, emotional and psychological needs are met for them to excel academically.

However, in Nigerian schools, many children are exposed to different forms of adversities. There

are reported and unreported cases of ACEs in the zone. The majority of the students in Obollo-Afor education zone live with their step-parents, half-brothers and sisters from where issues always come. Some of them have their parents divorced or separated, while some of them live as house help in a home where violence is high. Such experiences create self-doubt and fear in schoolchildren. It has been observed that children who have experienced ACEs struggle with the development of the cognitive abilities required for academic success. Poor motivation and low achievement orientation among schoolchildren have been linked to adverse childhood experiences (ACEs).

Several studies have investigated the impact of ACEs on children's academic outcome from different settings and have shown that exposure to ACEs is associated with poor academic motivation, reduced cognitive functioning, and low academic achievement among children. Despite these findings, there is limited empirical evidence on how these adverse experiences impact the achievement orientation among schoolchildren in Nigeria. In Obollo-Afor Education Zone specifically, little is known about the impact of adverse childhood experiences on achievement orientation among schoolchildren. The lack of empirical evidence in this area limits the efforts of stakeholders in education in supporting children exposed to ACEs. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the impact of adverse childhood experiences on achievement orientation among schoolchildren in the Obollo-Afor Education Zone of Nigeria.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this research is to ascertain the impact of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) on achievement orientation in Nigerian schoolchildren. The specific purpose is to:

- (a) ascertain the impact of ACEs on achievement orientation among Nigerian schoolchildren.
- (b) determine whether gender is associated with differences in achievement orientation among

school children exposed to adverse childhood experiences.

1.3. Research Hypotheses

The study was led by the following null hypotheses (H₀), tested at the 0.05 probability level (p<0.05):

H₀₁: Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) do not significantly impact achievement orientation score among school children.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the achievement orientation scores of male and female children exposed to adverse childhood experiences.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

This study used an ex-post facto research design. This design, according to Nworgu (2015), sought to determine cause-and-effect associations where the researcher typically does not influence the variables of the study. Ex-post facto design is suitable for the study because it explored how adverse childhood experiences impact achievement orientation among school children. In addition, ACEs, which is the independent variable cannot be manipulated by the researchers having occurred as early life experiences. However, the findings can only indicate associations between adverse childhood experiences and achievement orientation, and not establish definitive causal relationships since the ex-post facto research design does not involve manipulation of variables.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The Departmental of Educational Foundations Research Committee at the University of Nigeria provided ethical clearance for this study. In addition, permission of the principals of the schools was obtained for the study to be conducted in their schools. Also, written consent was obtained from the participants and their parents for them to participate in the study. Participants were assured

confidentiality and anonymity of their information.

2.2. Area of the Study

This study was conducted in public coeducational secondary schools in Obollo-Afor Education Zone, Enugu State, Nigeria and the headquarters is located in Obollo-Afor. The zone is made up of three local government areas, including Igbo-Eze North, Igbo-Eze South and Udenu. Igbo is the major spoken language in the area. A significant number of people in the area are Christians, while a good number of them follow African traditional religion, and a small number of them are Muslims. The inhabitants are comprised of civil servants, traders and farmers, and polygamy is commonly practiced. Based on that, a significant number of children in the area are subjected to childhood adversities. Moreover, there are not enough empirical studies ascertaining the impact of ACEs on achievement orientation among Nigerian school children. These conditions moved the researchers to find out if ACEs have an impact on the achievement orientation of Nigerian school children.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population of this study comprised all the 477 junior secondary school students in class 2 susceptible to adverse childhood experiences in all the 41 co-educational public secondary schools in Obollo-Afor Education Zone, Enugu state, Nigeria. Information pertaining to students' school adjustment and maladjustment behaviour such as poor discipline, consistence examination failure, absenteeism, and other school related problem was obtained from form teachers and school guidance counsellors. Using a purposive sampling procedure, all 477 students were screened with an ACEs checklist through a pre-survey instrument. Of these, 256 students (91 males, 165 females) were identified as exposed to ACEs, while 221 students (107 males, 114 females) had no exposure and served as a comparison group. Due to purposive sampling used, the findings may not be generalized

beyond junior secondary school students in Obollo-Afor Education Zone, Enugu State.

Recruitment of the participants was facilitated by school principals, class teachers, and counsellors, who used school records and the ACEs checklist to identify eligible participants. Inclusion criteria required that students be identified via the ACEs checklist, be junior secondary school students, and be no older than 13 years. Students not meeting these criteria were excluded. Due to the purposive sampling method, findings may not be generalized beyond junior secondary school students in Obollo-Afor Education Zone.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

This study made use of two instruments. These were: Adverse Childhood Experiences Questionnaire (ACEQ) and Students' Achievement Orientation Questionnaire (SAOQ). The ACEQ was adapted from the World Health Organisation's ACEs International Questionnaire (ACE-IQ; WHO, 2017). The original instrument was modified through the addition, removal, and rephrasing of items. The original 6-point and Yes/No response formats were revised into a 4-point Likert scale and restructured into statement form. The final ACEQ consisted of 33 negatively worded items covering three dimensions of ACEs: abuse, neglect, and household dysfunction, with demographic items excluded. Two versions of ACEQ were used. Version 1 served as ACEs proneness checklist with yes/no responses to identify students exposed to ACEs. Score of Yes = 1 and No = 0. Version 2 was used for data collection to assess the impact of ACEs among schoolchildren. Responses were rated on a 4-point scale of Always (4), Often (3), Rarely (2), and Never (1).

The Students' Achievement Orientation Questionnaire (SAOQ) was adapted from Achievement Goal Orientation Scale (AGOS) developed by Ouyang and Hutchinson (2008). The instrument was modified and contains 24 items. Most of the items were rephrased, and some discarded

to incorporate the different goals of achievement orientation (including mastery orientation, performance orientation, avoidance orientation and adjustment and well-being). Also, the items' response of 7-point scale was modified to a 4-point scale. The instrument sought to elicit information on the in-school adolescents' achievement orientation. On a 4-point scale, respondents indicate how much they agree with the item statement. The minimum score of the instrument is 24 and maximum score is 96. SAOQ score of 24- 48 are considered low achievement orientation while score of 49 and above are considered high achievement orientation. In this study, the instruments were validated by experts and trial tested. The reliability estimates of 0.89 was obtained for ACEQ while 0.70 was obtained for SAOQ using Cronbach Alpha method.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

Five research assistants assisted with the collection of data. Adverse Childhood Experiences Questionnaire (ACEQ) and Students' Achievement Orientation Questionnaire (SAOQ) were administered by research assistants on the spot.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

This study used ex-post facto research design. For data analysis, mean, standard deviation and ANOVA were used for data analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) do not significantly impact achievement orientation score among school children.

Table 1: Mean analysis of the achievement orientation scores of school children who were exposed to adverse childhood experiences and those who were not exposed

	N	Mea n	Std. Deviatio n	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Df	T	p
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
Exposed to ACEs	250	51.72	7.39	50.79	52.64			
Not Exposed to ACEs	221	53.89	8.42	52.77	55.00	469	-	.003
Total	471	52.73	7.96	52.01	53.45		2.978	

Data in Table 1 indicated a significant negative impact of adverse childhood experiences on achievement orientation of students, $t(469) = -2.978, p = .003$. This by implication shows that adversity during childhood has a major detrimental effect on achievement orientation of school children. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) do not significantly impact achievement orientation score among school children is rejected ($p < .05$).

3.2. Hypothesis two:

There is no significant difference in the achievement orientation scores of male and female children exposed to adverse childhood experiences.

Table 2: Mean analysis of the achievement orientation scores of male and female school children

	N	Mean	Std. Deviatio n	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Df	t	p
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
Male	195	52.67	8.25	51.51	53.84			
Female	276	52.78	7.76	51.86	53.70	469	-.142	.887
Total	471	52.73	7.96	52.01	53.45			

The data presented in table 2 indicated that male school children had a mean achievement orientation

score of 52.67 (SD = 8.25), while female school children had a mean score of 52.78 (SD = 7.76). The difference between the mean scores of male and female children was not statistically significant, $t(469) = -0.142, p = .887$. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the achievement orientation scores of male and female schoolchildren exposed to adverse childhood experiences was not rejected ($p > .05$). This implies that there is no significant difference in the achievement orientation of male and female children who are exposed to adverse childhood experiences.

3.4. Discussion

The results indicated a significant negative impact of adverse childhood experiences on achievement orientation among students who had ACEs than their counterparts. This by implication, shows that the achievement orientation of school children is negatively impacted by the adverse experiences they had as children. The results of this investigation are consistent with the study carried out by (Merrick, Ports, Ford, Afifi, Gershoff, & Grogan-Kaylor, 2017) on adverse childhood experiences and life opportunities, which showed that those who had been exposed to ACEs recorded high rates of school dropout, poverty, as well unemployment. A similar study by Blodgett and Lanigan (2018) indicated an interplay between the number of ACE and the likelihood of having behavioral problems, probability of low attendance, and failing to achieve a good grade in the core subjects. Another study from Kim, de Long, Gorelik, Penwell, Donovan and Chung (2020) found a diverse influence of family settings such as parent objectives and family orientations on children's adaptation mastery goals. This could mean that the development of new abilities is significantly impacted by a person's achievement orientation, as maybe observed from the way the students respond to their academic tasks. Their orientation affects how they think, behave, and feel inspired to learn and

complete a task (Hirt, Karlen, Merki, & Suter, 2021). This indicated that school children who were consistently exposed to early childhood adversity may not have the zeal to work hard to succeed in life or in terms of their academics rather, they may be concerned about how they will survive. This is not surprising because such may happen when parents or caregivers become uninvolved in assisting their children in academics through such activities as not providing for the children's needs, being unsupportive, or being too harsh on their children without reason, among others. Therefore, low achievement orientation leads to low desire to work.

Furthermore, the findings of this research revealed that gender does not significantly differentiate the achievement orientation of children exposed to adverse childhood experiences. Male and female children demonstrated similar levels of achievement orientation, indicating that exposure to ACEs affects both genders in comparable ways with respect to their achievement orientation. This finding suggests that the negative effects of adverse childhood experiences on achievement-related behaviours may operate independently of gender. Regardless of being male or female, schoolchildren exposed to ACEs may experience similar emotional, cognitive, and motivational challenges that shape their approach to learning and achievement.

The findings of this study align with the results of study conducted earlier by Musa, Dauda and Umar (2016) on gender differences in achievement goals of senior secondary school students and found no gender effects on achievement goals orientation of students. Similarly, Amoke, Ede, Umeano, Okeke, Onah, Ezeah and Nwaogaidu (2021) indicated in their findings that students' achievement orientation is not significantly impacted by gender. In other words, these studies showed no significant difference in achievement orientation of male and female school children. On the other hand, this present study contradicts the studies conducted by Žitniaková-Gurgová (2007) and Fouladchang,

Marzooghi, and Shemshiri (2009) that showed a significant influence of gender on achievement motivation of students and confirmed gender differences in achievement motivation variables. Based on the above discussion, it is possible that apart from gender, there might be other factors that impact the level of achievement orientation of students investigated such as individual differences, geographical location

Implication and Limitation

This study is not left without limitations despite its contribution regarding the impact of ACEs and achievement orientation. ACEs data is retrospective and there could be recall bias. Some children may have underreported their adverse experiences, while some may have overreported the adverse experiences they had, thereby raising concern over the accuracy of the data. Another limitation is that by focusing only on the school children, the study did not account for the experiences of out-of-school children who may have had more severe adverse experiences, and their achievement are often ignored, thereby limiting the generalizability of the findings beyond the study population.

Based on these findings, this study recommended that parents and adults who have custody of children should be made aware of the negative effects that ACEs have on people during childhood and later in life, as well as the ways that ACEs can be prevented in the home, at school, and in the community. Parents should also not discriminate against any gender or have gender preference. The study further recommended that regular checks should be done in school settings to assist those who are vulnerable to adverse experiences.

4. Conclusion

Conclusion of this study is based on its findings and discussion. This study has shown that most of the school children live with negative childhood experiences that are linked to risk factor for many

negative life outcomes such as low achievement orientation among school children. Charity, “they say begins at home”, and if the home is not caring and supportive, there is the likelihood for the student’s achievement orientation to be low irrespective of their gender. Therefore, adverse childhood experiences do not exacerbate gender differences in achievement orientation among school children who are victims of ACEs.

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest to declare by the authors.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: P. O. A

Design: P. O. A

Analysis and Interpretation of Results: P. O. A

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Data Availability Statement

Data will be made available on request

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